

Making Archives Explorable: Visualising Digital Materials for a Wider Public

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Three Views of the Ben-Gavriël Guestbook

Lazarus Archive Folder

Introduction

The research project “A Fresh Look. Visualising Digitised German-Jewish Archives” at the Cluster of Excellence “Understanding Written Artefacts” and the Hub of Computing and Data Science at the University of Hamburg aims to

investigate human information-seeking strategies in archival contexts that go beyond targeted, systematic searching. In the digital context, appropriate and user-friendly visualisation solutions can enable and facilitate an exploratory approach and increase the probability of serendipitous discoveries by the metaphorical “information flaneur” (Dörk et al. 2011). The project experiments with novel representations while preserving the original context of the historical artefact, and we present two use cases below.

Ben-Gavriël Guestbook

We developed a digital edition of the guestbook of the artist couple Miryam Ben-Gavriël (born Martha Schnabel, 1893–1980) and Moshe Ya’akov Ben-Gavriël (born Eugen Hoeflich, 1891–1965), whose Jerusalem home was a place of cross-cultural gathering and intellectual encounter. Nearly 1,200 individual entries in the form of signatures, greetings, dedications, poems and drawings in German, Hebrew, English, French, Arabic and more than a dozen other languages provide a fascinating glimpse into the personal and professional networks of the Ben-Gavriëls between 1927 and the husband’s death in 1965 (Schirrmeister 2025). The entries have been transcribed and translated by hand and wherever possible, visitors’ names have been linked to the relevant authority files (VIAF, GND, Wikidata).

A landing page provides details of the project and three contrasting views of the data: one using Vikus Viewer¹ (Glinka et al. 2017), one based around the OpenSeadragon visualization library (Gilman et al, 2024) and the third a network diagram using the d3js data visualization library². The first provides a quantitative timeline, grouping the entries by year and allowing search by keywords and full-text search of the metadata. The second is a digital twin of the archival artefact and allows a user to browse the book page by page. In these views, selecting a guestbook entry provides a pop-up panel containing structured metadata and other sources of information. The third view allows a user to explore the relationships between visitors and events recorded in the guestbook. The three viewers are interlinked, allowing users to switch easily between the perspectives. The landing page also provides an alphabetical list of names with links to the digital twin view.

Moritz Lazarus Archive

The second stage of the project is based on a much larger archive, the written estate of German-Jewish philosopher Moritz Lazarus³. The archive has been repeatedly divided, rearranged, and supplemented, and currently consists of 208 archival folders in four series containing more than 37,000 images. The content is digitized but metadata is only available at the folder level, and multi-page documents have been separated into individual images with no explicit connection, making a digital twin view impossible. The challenge in this case is to present the data in a manner which

will encourage visitors to explore and engage with the archive.

We aim to create a fully browsable, immersive virtual representation of the entire archive, using Vikus Viewer to display the individual pages ordered by folder, with options for filtering based on terms in the metadata, extracted from the record descriptions using Voyant Tools⁴ text analysis and manually evaluated for relevance. We will also provide scatter plots based on image similarity, allowing users to see documents of different types grouped together, for instance postcards, typed sheets or handwritten letters. We also plan to investigate the use of OCR on typed and handwritten documents to improve their accessibility and enable further post-processing such as content classification and metadata enhancement.

Conclusions and Future Work

Working on these two archives shows the scope of possibilities and requirements posed by archives of different size and information granularity. Detailed metadata can allow for rich interconnectivity both within the resource and in a wider context, enabling visitors to wander at liberty through the information landscape. Where this metadata is not yet available, we explore the use of OCR and language technologies to unearth it. We will use the experiences gained from these projects to inform future work with digitized archives of varying sizes and make them accessible and attractive to a wide public.

Footnotes

1. <https://github.com/cpietsch/vikus-viewer>
2. <https://d3js.org/>
3. https://www.nli.org.il/en/archives/NNL_ARCHI-VE_AL990026948100205171/NLI
4. <http://voyant-tools.org/>

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